

Dyeing of Cotton Woven Fabric Using Sustainable Natural Dye (Date Leaves) and Bio-Mordants

Sumi Akter

BGMEA University of Fashion & Technology, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Mahmuda Chowdhury

BGMEA University of Fashion & Technology, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Tahmina Akhter

Northern University of Bangladesh, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Md. Alimur Reza

BGMEA University of Fashion & Technology, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Shohanur Rahman

BGMEA University of Fashion & Technology, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Suggested Citation

Akter, S., Chowdhury, M., Akhter, T., Reza, M.A., & Rahman, S. (2024). Dyeing of Cotton Woven Fabric Using Sustainable Natural Dye (Date Leaves) and Bio-Mordants. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(5), 569-578.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(5\).54](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(5).54)

Abstract:

This study on natural dyes has been chosen for a sustainable dyeing method on textile through the using of 99% cotton 1% spandex woven fabric. The dye was produced from the Date Palm Leaf (*Phoenix dactylifera* L) using Soxhlet machine through continuous extraction method and dyed using natural bio-mordant eucalyptus, guava leaf. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) test was carried for nanoparticle characterization along with color measurements with specular and UV include mode. The dyed fabrics were also assessed for wash fastness, fastness against perspiration, dry rubbing and wet rubbing property. In most of the cases the fastness property of sample without mordant is better than with

mordant. Cotton fabric is used for dyeing to make it sustainable and to reduce the dependency on synthetic dyes; the natural material can also reduce the pressure on synthetic material.

Keywords: *Sustainable natural dye, Bio-mordant, Soxhlet extraction, Color strength, Fastness properties.*

Introduction

Natural fibers have always been an important resource for the textiles. With the rise of synthetic fibers, natural fibers have reduced in use. Natural resources along with fibers are being used mostly in recent times (Noureddine Baaka, 2023; Khan, 2019). The most prevalent and frequently utilized natural fiber today is cotton. Cotton's popularity stems from its many

quality-enhancing characteristics (Sam-Jung Kim a, 2008; Grammatikos, 2019). Humanity only used natural dyes made from plant leaves, roots, bark, insect secretions, and minerals to color textiles until the first synthetic dye was discovered in 1856 (Samanta, 2009). Natural dye has uncovered a new source of eco-friendly, efficient and inexpensive dye for textiles as well as other industry though synthetic dyes rose to popularity in nineteenth century due to some

advantages (Baaka, 2020; Freeman, 2023; Jyoti Arora, 2017). As per the report of World Bank, it is found that synthetic textile dyes cause 17-20% of industrial water pollution, and around 40% of synthetic dyes include recognized carcinogens. In addition, chemical dyes can build in rivers, producing harmful, hormone disrupting compounds that cause animal abnormalities and death (Kant, 2012)

Natural dyes can be produced from various components of nature and it may be of plant-based, animal-based, mineral-based, or microbial-based colors, according to origin (M. Iftikhar Hussain Muhammad Farooq, 2020). Natural dyes from stem of plants are popular due their sustainability (Kiron, Natural Dyes: Properties, Classification, Production, Advantages and Disadvantages, 2022). A lot of research has been carried out on Phoenix Dactylifera Linn but there are scope to work (Vayalil, 2012). Date leaves are long, pinnate fronds that are harvested from the date palm tree and used to make traditional handicrafts like mats and baskets (Elsadig Mahdi a, 2021). Furthermore, there is little scientific proof that date leaves have antioxidant qualities. Food can be wrapped in the culinary arts to add flavor and retain moisture while cooking (Badara Gueye, 2009).

With their glossy, lance-shaped structure, eucalyptus leaves are known for their unique aroma, which is attributed to the presence of essential oils, including eucalyptol (T. Takahashi, 2004). These leaves are used in a variety of ways in essential oil manufacturing, aromatherapy, and cosmetics. Due to the possibility of toxicity in excessive doses, care should be taken, and seeking medical advice prior to therapeutic usage is advised (Khaled Sebei, 2015).

The leaves of the guava tree, which is native to Central America and is abundantly grown in Bangladesh, are used in traditional medicine to cure conditions like respiratory disorders and diarrhea (Jongkwon Seo, 2014). They are thought to possess antibacterial activity that promotes a healthy gut flora besides anti-inflammatory qualities helpful for ailments like arthritis (Suganya Tachakittirungrod, 2007).

Since the issue has been revealed in regards to natural fibers and tints, there hasn't been much research conducted concerning cotton fabric. A lot of prior study has been concentrated on the beneficial effects of including bio mordants to botanical extracts and how to do so. On the other hand, little is known about the inherent properties of dyestuffs having these bio mordants. Yet multi-mordanting with biological mordants are not so practiced, synthetic mordants have been employed in previous experiments. The goals of this experiment is to discover how date leaves may be utilized as a renewable and environmentally sound natural dye for cotton fabrics including and excluding bio-mordant. To get better color fastness features, the study optimizes the extraction method and finds the ideal dyeing parameters, including pH, temperature, and duration. Biological mordants outperform metallic ones in this context (Marwa Souissi, 2018).

Little solvent is required for Soxhlet extraction method for natural dye which is an economical approach. It uses the principles of solvent reflux and siphon to provide high efficiency, solvent conservation, and continuous extraction of solid matter (M.U. Kaison G.Y. Pam, 2014). The solid sample is kept in a Soxhlet extractor fitted with filter paper and then the solvent is sipped back. Solvent is included, heated, and the the vapors are allowed to extract soluble components (Yahyavi, 2020).

The overall process of dyeing with natural dye need a detailed assessment of the technique of dyeing, with a particular emphasis on the assessment of colorfastness, wash-fastness, and lightfastness in post-dyeing cotton fabric. This research aims to expand existing knowledge on sustainable dyeing processes, with a target on cotton woven textiles. It also intends to provide vital insights and practical ideas for textile enterprises and crafts people interested in implementing ecologically conscious and sustainable dyeing processes with date leaves and bio mordant (Kiron, 2022; A. Kumar Samanta, 2020).

Due to a lot of technical and sustainability terms, the textile industry's overall usage of natural dyes

is still quite low, at about 1% (Safapour, 2013). These problems include the lack of easily accessible standard forms, machine incompatibility, and a restricted range of non-reproducible colors. Since natural dyes being easily degradable and regenerative, they are sustainable too (Jyoti Arora, 2017). However, It has limitations including poor reproducibility, limited availability, cost inefficiency, inadequate color fixation, and subpar colorfastness properties (Gokhale, 2004). Enzymatic catalysis is such an effective method for green and sustainable way for dyeing textiles (Long Bai a b, 2016).

Materials and Methods

Materials

Cotton denim fabric was used here to dye where the composition is 99% cotton with 1% spandex and the fabric is of 380 gsm; The fabric has EPI and PPI of 48 & 28 respectively.

Chemicals

The dye along with mordants were collected from nature collected from local area of Bangladesh. Dye was extracted from date leaves and bio-mordants from guava leaf, and eucalyptus leaf. Salt, soda ash and hydrogen peroxide used here were bought from local market of Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Dye Extraction

Fresh green leaves was gathered for dyes extraction which were dried properly before extraction. Then dried leaves were cut into small pieces, for each cycle on Soxhlet 300ml ethanol (C_2H_5OH) of 5% concentration taken. The Soxhlet machine consists of a thimble, which contains the sample to be extracted, and a flask with the solvent. The flask heated at $85^{\circ}C$, causing the solvent to vaporize and pass through the thimble, extracting the dye from the sample. The vaporized solvent then condensed in a condenser and dripped back to the flask, where it was reheated and the process repeated. 22gm of leaves were added for a single extraction.

Mordant Extraction

Eucalyptus and guava leaves were extracted through Soxhlet extraction process and similarly the sample weighted before extraction and both mordant extracted in similar chemical concentration. In every intake of extraction 22g of crushed leaves filled into the cylindrical shape filter paper. The white paper inside the solvent flask is filter paper being used to protect the crushed to prevent the contamination of dyes. Exactly 300ml ethanol (C_2H_5OH) of 5% concentration taken. In one extraction leaves were filled once and thus extraction completed by three cycle. First cycle took around 3 hours to complete then 2nd cycle took around 2 hours and the last cycle took almost 1.5 hours to be complete. After these step the dyes collected to another container then leave for few minutes to cool down.

Dyeing Process

Mordant influence the color property of dyed material it enhance the fastness and help to fixed properly. Several mordanting technique has been used for the study in single mordanting method the unfinished sample token the scoured and bleached fabric was immersed in the the dyeing pot out at $80^{\circ}C$ temperature for 60 minute at liquor ratio 1:30. After dyeing the sample treated soap wash for few minute and then dried the sample at ambient temperature.

In multiple mordanting the mordant mixed along with dyes. The calculated amount of mordant token in the dye bath and then similarly dyes added to the dye bath as per liquor ratio. In this method the dyeing carried out for a long duration more then 60 minute at $80^{\circ}C$ where mordant and dyes get enough time to being chemically active and to fixed properly. After dyeing the sample washed and dried at ambient temperature. For the sample without mordant is dyed only with the dye produced from date leaf.

Experimental Work

K/S Value

The K/S value determines the color strength. It is measured by the light reflectance technique

using the Kubelka-Munk equation (MICHAEL L. MYRICK, 2011). The reflectance of dyed sample fabrics were measured. The reflectance or transmittance of the fabrics are not directly related to the colorant concentrations. Rather the derived Kubelka-Munk function from reflectance is directly related to the concentration of colorants. As per theory, the ratio between the absorption and scattering coefficients of the colorant is directly proportional to its concentration that is additive in mixture. The color strength is measured by value of K/S ratio of two samples at one wavelength (λ max) or the values are summed at intervals 10 or 20 nm over every wavelength in the visible spectrum (A.R. Khataee a, 2010).

$$k / s = (1 - 2RR)2 \quad (1)$$

Where K is the sorption coefficient, R is the reflectance of dyed fabric and S is the scattering coefficient (J. Rodgers*, 2008; Ari, 2019).

FTIR

FTIR stands for Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy. It's a technique used in analytical chemistry and materials science to identify and characterize chemical compounds as per their infrared absorption spectra. FTIR spectroscopy measures the interaction of infrared radiation with a sample, providing information regarding the molecular structure, functional groups, and chemical composition. Spectra were attained in the range of 4000 to 500 cm^{-1} . 32 scans were taken at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . FTIR spectroscopy has varieties of applications in different fields, including pharmaceuticals, polymers, textile, chemicals, food and beverages, forensic science, environmental science, and materials science. A powerful analytical tool that can provide qualitative and quantitative information of chemical composition and structure for wide range of samples, including liquids, solids, and gases (Zanyar Movasaghi, 2008).

The fragmented state of the textiles allowed for a non-invasive approach, as loose fragments

were temporarily removed for analysis and then returned. Each fragment or sample was placed on a small gold mirror fitted into the central hole of a microscope slide, with the microscope aperture set at $70 \times 100 \mu\text{m}$. Utilizing the fragmented nature of the textiles and the non-destructive nature of FTIR microscopy in reflectance mode, numerous samples ranging in size from approximately $2 \times 2 \text{ mm}$ to $5 \times 5 \text{ mm}$ were analyzed. Ten different areas of each sample were examined, five for the warps and five for the wefts. Consistent spectra were synthesized to produce an average spectrum. This was done to verify the presence of characteristic peaks for the major organic polymers in the samples (Schmitt, 1998).

Washing Fastness

The dyed samples were washed to ISO 105-C06 C2S standard. The size of the sample was 100 mm \times 40 mm. The wash bath contained 4 g/l ECE phosphate reference detergent, the temperature of the bath was 60°C and time of washing 30 minutes. 25 stainless steel globules were added into each bath to perform washing. After washing, the sample were rinsed twice in deionized water and air dried at room temperature.

Rubbing Fastness

In ISO-105-X-12 the wet pickup of the rubbing cloth is 100%. We check rubbing by Dry and Wet methods. In wet rubbing we wet the rubbing cloth according to test method and give rating by comparing the Staining with the gray scale. Similarly for dry rubbing we check the rubbing with dry rubbing cloth and compare the staining with gray scale for ratings. Color fastness to rubbing is a main test which is always required for every colored fabric. The dyed samples were test according to ISO 105 X-12 standard. The size of the sample was 50 x 130 mm, arm is weighted to provide a constant 9N load on the sample at all times and a mechanical counter keeps track of completed 10 cycles. After the process rubbing fastness samples are ready. Then it is compared AATCC gray scale for staining of color.

Result & Discussion

Measurement of Color

The sample dyes using natural guava and eucalyptus extract mordant are observed by CIELab system of spectrophotometer. The lightness value L^* show higher lightness value for non mordanting. The lightness value is lower for eucalyptus mordanting dyed sample, the result show the brightness of these dyed sample

which indicate the great brightness for non mordant sample. The guava mordant sample and combined mordant sample shows moderate brightness. The positive values of a^* and b^* indicate the redness and yellowness, the dyed sample show the negative a^* value which indicate the greenness and both combined show the value of greenness and yellowness. Where eucalyptus mordant sample show higher greenness effect and guava mordant offer higher yellowness value.

Table 1. Measurement of Color Strength

Mordant	DL*	Da*	Db*	K/S	Sample
Without mordant	5.92	-3.988	3.205	2.055	
Guava	4.027	-1.589	5.617	3.204	
Eucalyptus	3.061	-4.392	3.761	2.613	
Guava & Eucalyptus	3.62	-2.932	4.163	3.402	

The analytical data from k/s value helps to measure the color or shade depth reduction of any dyed sample by calculating the ratio between before wash and after wash k/s value. The data from the table which indicate the higher k/s value for combined mordant sample. After consistent wash the closer value indicate better shade depth. Among these three samples, non mordant could be said poor color strength.

Measurement of Fastness Property

Color fastness to wash

Natural dyes such as guava and eucalyptus have different staining values on different textiles; a

combined extract of guava and eucalyptus achieves a staining value of 5, which indicates a deep penetration of color. Cotton stains less than polyester or acrylic, which have higher values (4/5). Different fabrics react differently. In textile applications, it is essential to comprehend these staining values in order to avoid unwanted color migration, particularly with high-staining textiles. Guava and eucalyptus work together to create a vivid, complex color interaction that highlights the dyeing technique' versatility.

Table 2. Color Staining

Mordanting	Color staining to					
	Wool	Acrylic	Polyester	Nylon	Cotton	Acetate
Without Mordant (1)	3	4/5	4	4	2/3	4
Guava (2)	3/4	4	4/5	5	3	4/5
Eucalyptus (3)	3	4	4/5	4/5	3	4
Guava & Eucalyptus (4)	3/4	5	4/5	5	2	4/5

Figure 1. Color Fastness to Wash (Staining Value)

Table 3. Color Fading

Mordanting	Color fading to					
	Wool	Acrylic	Polyester	Nylon	Cotton	Acetate
Without Mordant (1)	2	2	1/2	1	4	1
Guava (2)	4	1	1	1	2	4
Eucalyptus (3)	2	1/2	1	4	2	1
Guava & Eucalyptus (4)	4	1	1	2	3	4

Figure 2. Color Fastness to Wash (Fading Value)

The findings imply that, in comparison to separate dyes, Acrylic and Nylon exhibit greater colorfastness for the Guava & Eucalyptus blend. In contrast, cotton in the blend shows less colorfastness than guava alone. Remember that these scores may differ depending on industry standards or testing procedures, and they are based on a broad interpretation.

Color Fastness to Rubbing

Table 4. Color Fastness to Rubbing

Mordanting	Rubbing Fastness	
	Dry State	Wet State
Non	4	3
Guava	4/5	3
Eucalyptus	4/5	3/4
Guava & Eucalyptus	4/5	3/4

Figure 3. Color Fastness to Rubbing

From the observation of these two color fastness table we can compare the fastness property of sample 1 where dyed without mordant very good compared to others.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) Analysis

a. Sample dyed with eucalyptus mordant

b. Sample dyed with guava leaf mordant

c. Sample dyed without mordant

d. Sample dyed guava & eucalyptus mordant

Figure 4. FTIR Analysis of Four Different Dyed Samples

It is being seen that the date plant leaf contains carbohydrates, alkaloids, steroids, flavonoids, saponins and tannins. In FTIR graphs the pick around 3400cm^{-1} vibrational stretching of OH group is for cellulose as well as Phoenix *Dactylifera* L. between the range of (3300cm^{-1} to 3400cm^{-1}) has the higher intensity of hydrogen-bond but more than 3410cm^{-1} have negligible intensity. The vibrational stretching undergoes at the point around 2850cm^{-1} which shows symmetric stretching of $-\text{CH}_2$ (cutine and wax).

P. Dactylifera shows a sharp peak at 1593cm^{-1} is a primary amine N-H, primary amines show overtone between (1590cm^{-1} – 1650cm^{-1}). N-H participated in bonding carbon of cellulose. The characteristic peaks of reaction product corresponding to C-O of a primary alcohol was at 1057cm^{-1} and it may indicate the presence of cellulose and hemicellulose. Peaks in this region (900cm^{-1} to 675cm^{-1}) can also be attributed to the presence of tannin in the evaluated extract. On the basis of FTIR analysis it could be said that the presences of carbodiimide, amine, alcohol and tannin are strongly observed. 1,2-disubstituted and 1,2,3-tridistituted C-H strong bond visible in Non mordant sample the process unable to break the bond in this region which means less affinity to fabric. 1685cm^{-1} - 1666cm^{-1} here strong conjugated keton is present moreover, after dyeing there is noticeable deposition of CO_2 in 2200cm^{-1} to 2400cm^{-1} . Overall dyeing result the graph derived from guava mordant provided the most distorted data, which means the presence of new bond and compound.

Conclusion & Recommendation

On the study of (*Phoenix dactylifera* Linn) it could be said that it's a potential source for natural dyeing. From the analytical data of the extract get the presence of tannins which is a quality enhancing property for natural dye. The soxhlet extraction method of the dyes is much user friendly and eco-friendly. Utilization of Date Palm Leaf processing industries will lead to

transforming a residue into a useful colouring matter for textile industry. As plant is the source of dyes so that the availability is required for commercialize and this plant is mostly available in the rural side of country. Moreover using mordant in minimal amount the result of dyeing is satisfactory for cotton fabric. Toxic chemical free dyeing made the process more sustainable though dyeing with bio mordant could provide more sustainable result. The analytical study on waste water said that this dye bath could be beneficial for ETP. This could be decide that using this dye has an acceptable growing on textile application. It will be an non-hazardous dyeing process.

References

- Ari, G. B. (2019). Evaluation of color strength (K/S) values of cotton fabrics dyed with reactive dye and treated with silver nanoparticles. *AIP Conference Proceedings*.
<https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5126341>
- Arora, J., & Agarwal, P. (2017). Rainbow of natural dyes on textiles using plant extracts: Sustainable and eco-friendly processes. *Green and Sustainable Chemistry*, 7(1), 1-10.
<https://doi.org/10.4236/gsc.2017.71001>
- Baaka, N. (2020). Sustainable dyeing of wool fabric using kermes oak (*Quercus coccifera* L.) as a source of natural colorant. *Journal of Natural Fibers*, 17(1), 37-45.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15440478.2020.1712184>
- Baaka, N., & Khalid, R. (2023). Ecofriendly dyeing of textile materials with natural colorants from date palm fiber fibrillum. *Sustainability*, 12(8), 1550.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su15081550>
- Bai, L., & Huang, S. (2016). Fabrication of oil-in-water nanoemulsions by dual-channel microfluidization using natural emulsifiers: Saponins, phospholipids, proteins, and polysaccharides. *Food Hydrocolloids*, 261, 703-711.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodhyd.2015.04.022>

- Foaisal, A. A. (2019). A review on sustainable textile products from jute and cotton blends. *Journal of Science and Engineering*, 13(3), 17-25.
- Freeman, H. S. (2023). Mordant dye application on cotton: Optimization and combination with natural dyes. *Coloration Technology*, 136(6), 647-655. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cote.12557>
- Gokhale, S. B. (2004). *Natural dye yielding plants*. CSIR.
- Grammatikos, A. D. (2019). Comparative life cycle assessment of cotton and other natural fibers for textile applications. *Fibers*, 7(1), 13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fib7010013>
- Gueye, B. F. M.-B.-L. (2009). Acquisition of callogenic capacity in date palm leaf tissues in response to 2,4-D treatment. *Journal of Plant Biotechnology*, 99(1), 35-45.
- Haji, M. M. (2013). Physical and mechanical properties of cotton/spandex fabrics. *Gale Academic OneFile*.
- Hashim, F., Ibrahim, H., & Samad, R. (2016). Properties and characterization of Mengkuang leaf fiber-filled ethylene vinyl acetate/natural rubber blend: Effects of blending sequences and Mengkuang leaf fiber loading. *Journal of Vinyl and Additive Technology*, 22(4), 233-240. <https://doi.org/10.1002/vnl.21459>
- Hussain, M. I., Farooq, M., & Akhtar, Q. (2020). Nutritional and biological characteristics of the date palm fruit (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) – A review. *Food Bioscience*, 34, 100509. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbio.2020.100509>
- Kader, S. H. (2015). Excellent dyeing properties of a natural dye extracted from the leaves of *Phoenix dactylifera* Linn on cotton and silk fabrics. *Journal of Natural Fibers*, 19(22), 9803-9812. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15440478.2015.1005317>
- Kaisan, M. U., Pam, G. Y., & Daku, K. (2014). Effects of oil extraction methods on biodiesel production from wild grape seeds: A case study of Soxhlet extraction and mechanical press engine-driven expeller methods. *Journal of Alternate Energy Sources and Technologies*, 6(1), 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2022.101563>
- Kant, R. (2012). Textile dyeing industry: An environmental hazard. *Natural Science*, 4(1), 22-29. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ns.2012.41004>
- Khan, K. N. (2019). Natural fiber-reinforced polymer composites: History, types, advantages and applications. *Materials Engineering Research*, 1(2), 12-20. <https://doi.org/10.30564/mer.v1i2.1157>
- Khataee, A. R., & Kasiri, M. B. (2010). Photocatalytic degradation of organic dyes in the presence of nanostructured titanium dioxide: Influence of the chemical structure of dyes. *Journal of Molecular Catalysis A: Chemical*, 328(1-2), 8-26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molcata.2010.05.023>
- Kim, S.-J., Moon, J.-B., & Hwang, M.-H. (2008). Mechanical properties of polypropylene/natural fiber composites: Comparison of wood fiber and cotton fiber. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 27(7), 801-806. <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.24825>
- Kiron, M. I. (2022). Natural dyes: Properties, classification, production, advantages, and disadvantages. *Textile Learner*, 12(1), 12-14. <https://doi.org/10.15406/jnsft.2022.11.00053>
- Kiron, M. I. (2022). Natural dyes: Properties, classification, production, advantages and disadvantages. *Textile Learner*, 12-14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tibtech.2017.03.012>
- Kumar Samanta, A. (2020). Bio-Dyes, Bio-Mordanta and Bio-Finishes: Scientific analysis for their application on textiles. In *Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments* (pp. 1-50).
- Mahdi, E., Rojek, D., & Hussain, A. R. (2021). Khalasa date palm leaf fiber as a potential reinforcement for polymeric composite materials. *Materials Today Communications*, 26(1), 265. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtcomm.2020.101772>
- Movasaghi, Z., & Rehman, S. (2008). Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy of biological tissues. *Applied Spectroscopy Reviews*, 43(02), 134-179. <https://doi.org/10.1080/05704920701829043>

- Myrick, M. L., & Prather, B. L. (2011). The Kubelka-Munk diffuse reflectance formula revisited. *Applied Spectroscopy Reviews*, 46(4), 240-263.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/05704928.2011.553120>
- Prati, S. (2016). Analyses of trace amounts of dyes with a new enhanced sensitivity FTIR spectroscopic technique: MU-ATR (metal underlayer ATR spectroscopy). *Vibrational Spectroscopy*, 85, 941.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vibspec.2016.04.007>
- Rodgers, J., & George, T. (2008). Instrumental and operational impacts on spectrophotometer color measurements. *The Journal of Cotton Science*, 12(1), 287-297.
- Safapour, M. B. (2013). Natural dyes and antimicrobials for green treatment of textiles. *Environmental Chemistry Letters*, 1(3), 129-136.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10311-013-0410-1>
- Samanta, A. K. (2009). Application of natural dyes on textiles. *Indian Journal of Fibre & Textile Research*, 34(4), 384-399.
- Schmitt, J. (1998). FTIR-spectroscopy in microbial and material analysis. *International Biodeterioration & Biodegradation*, 41(01), 41-48.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0964-8305\(98\)00038-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0964-8305(98)00038-4)
- Sebei, K., & Shakib, F. (2015). Chemical composition and antibacterial activities of seven Eucalyptus species essential oil leaves. *Springer Nature*.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/springer-2119784>
- Senthilkumar, M. (2012). Effect of spandex input tension, spandex linear density and cotton yarn loop length on dynamic elastic behavior of cotton/spandex knitted fabrics. *Indian Journal of Fibre & Textile Research*, 7(4), 400-405.
- Seo, J., & Lee, S. (2014). Study to find the best extraction solvent for use with guava leaves (*Psidium guajava* L.) for high antioxidant efficacy. *Food Science and Nutrition*, 2(2), 174-180.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/fsn3.94>
- Shahid, M., & Faiz, S.-u.-I. (2013). Recent advancements in natural dye applications: A review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 53, 310-331.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2013.04.004>
- Sheet, P. (2008). Basic 6-Place Soxhlet Extraction System Less Glassware & Connections 220-240V 50/60Hz 1Ph. *Journal of Chromatography*, 1-2.
- Souissi, M., Guesmi, A., & Gargouri, M. (2018). Valorization of natural dye extracted from date palm pits (*Phoenix dactylifera*) for dyeing of cotton fabric. Part 2: Optimization of dyeing process and improvement of colorfastness with biological mordants. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 204, 1143-1153.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.08.310>
- Tachakittirungrod, S., & O'Mahony, S. (2007). Study on antioxidant activity of certain plants in Thailand: Mechanism of antioxidant action of guava leaf extract. *Food Chemistry*, 103(2), 381-388.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2006.07.023>
- Takahashi, T., Kawamura, R., & Kimura, S. (2004). Antimicrobial activities of eucalyptus leaf extracts and flavonoids from *Eucalyptus maculata*. *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy*, 39(1), 60-64.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/39.1.60>
- Vayalil, P. K. (2012). Date fruits (*Phoenix dactylifera* Linn): An emerging medicinal food. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 52(3), 249-271.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2010.500234>
- Yahyavi, P. J. (2020). Extraction of phytosterols and tocopherols from rapeseed oil waste by supercritical CO₂ plus co-solvent: A comparison with conventional solvent extraction. *Heliyon*, 6(8), e04645.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04645>
- Zou, Y., & Ren, N. (2011). Reusing polyester/cotton blend fabrics for composites. *Composites Science and Technology*, 71(8), 763-770.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2011.03.003>